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Students' Perception of Teacher Effectiveness and Academic Achievement in Mathematics Among Secondary School Students in Abak Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between students' perceptions of teacher effectiveness and academic performance in mathematics among Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students in Abak Local Government Area (LGA) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was used in the study. The target population comprised all the 1,120 students enrolled in SS2 in the fourteen public secondary schools in Abak LGA. The study used a two-stage sampling procedure which combined purposive and systematic random sampling. A sample of 100 students (including 50 male and 50 female) was selected from five schools across Abak LGA. The instrument for data collection was the Students' Perception of Teacher Effectiveness Scale (SPTES), which contained 36 items across six subscales: General Performance, Clarity in Communication, Teaching Skill, Organisational Ability,

Cooperativeness, and Sense of Humour. The instrument was pilot-tested on 20 students (separate from the main sample) and achieved a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.81. The six null hypotheses were tested using the Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient at the 0.05 level of significance. The students' most recent mathematics examination scores were used as the measure of academic performance. All the six hypotheses were rejected. Statistically significant positive associations were found between each dimension of perceived teacher effectiveness and mathematics performance. The findings show that good students' impressions of their teachers go a long way to shaping learning outcomes in mathematics. The study recommends that instructional clarity, lesson organisation, and cooperative classroom practices should be prioritised by mathematics teachers and that student perception data be routinely incorporated into teacher appraisal processes.

Keywords: mathematics performance, teacher effectiveness, students' perception, secondary school students, instructional effectiveness

1.1 Introduction

Learning is a lifelong activity, and the teacher is an integral part of that process, especially in formal education (Allison Academy, 2023). The quality of education is directly determined by the quality of its teachers. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) stipulates that all teachers in the educational institutions shall be professionally trained and shall be structured to equip teachers for the effective performance of their duties. Based on this, students are left with the teachers for long hours; with this assurance of safety and professionalism, the teacher is described as a pilot of the educational enterprise because through the teacher, the curriculum is translated into classroom realities.

Perception, as defined by Murphy (1972), is the cognitive process through which sensory information is coded and given meaning. Perception involves seeing, hearing, and interpreting what is observed (Albert, 1966). This process forms the basis through which students form impressions about their teacher's instructional

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behaviours. These impressions, whether favourable or unfavourable, shape students' emotional dispositions towards the subject and, consequently, their engagement and performance (Kyriacou, 1986).

The scientific and technological development of any nation depends on the efforts made by such a nation to advance her students' learning of mathematics and other mathematical sciences (Wonu & Arokoyu, 2016). The subject is a compulsory component of secondary school curricula across Nigeria, and performance in it is widely used as a gateway criterion for tertiary admission. Despite the central role of numeracy in different contexts and everyday situations, children's underachievement in mathematics remains a consistent and significant problem (Dowker, 2004). Also, students continue to record poor outcomes in national examinations (West African Examinations Council [WAEC], 2024; Ibrahim & Maude, 2022).

Due to the global awareness of the importance of mathematical knowledge on one hand and the concern expressed for many years at various levels of education about underachievement in mathematics (Eng et al., 2010), the performance of students in mathematics from primary school to higher education is still a topic of concern (Wahid et al., 2014).

Since poor performance in mathematics indirectly affects students' overall academic outcomes, there is an urgent need to investigate the factors driving this trend at the secondary school level (Brezavšček et al., 2020). Researchers have attributed this persistent underachievement to a range of factors, including large class sizes, inadequate instructional materials, teacher effectiveness, weak foundational knowledge from primary school, and socio-economic barriers.

Despite the growth of teacher effectiveness research in Nigeria, rigorous studies that directly assess multiple dimensions of how students perceive their teachers' effectiveness at the secondary school level in Akwa Ibom State remain comparatively scarce. This study intends to address that gap. It examines how SS2 students in Abak LGA evaluate their mathematics teachers across six dimensions of effectiveness and whether these evaluations are significantly related to mathematics performance. The study's findings are intended to generate contextualised, actionable evidence for educational policy and professional development practice at state and national levels.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Mathematics has been described as a widely feared subject among Nigerian secondary school students (Ibrahim & Maude, 2022; WAEC, 2024). Despite its compulsory status and its centrality to higher education admission, students consistently record poor performance in national examinations. This poor performance has practical consequences: it limits students' access to science-related tertiary programmes, reduces their career options, and undermines national capacity for technological and economic development. However, a consistent body of evidence implicates the teacher as the most proximate determinant of learning outcomes (Ayanwoye et al., 2024). The way students in Akwa Ibom State perceive the effectiveness of their mathematics teachers and how those perceptions are meaningfully related to their academic achievement have not been researched adequately in previous studies; hence, this study is designed to fill this gap.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between students' perception of teacher effectiveness and academic performance in mathematics among SSII students in Abak LGA. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Determine whether students' perception of their teachers' general effectiveness was related to mathematics performance.
- ii. Examine whether students' rating of their teachers' clarity in communication was associated with mathematics achievement.
- iii. Investigate whether students' perception of teaching skill effectiveness was related to mathematics grades.
- iv. Assess whether students' rating of teachers' organising ability was associated with mathematics achievement.
- v. Determine whether students' perception of teacher cooperativeness was related to mathematics performance.
- vi. Examine whether students' perception of teachers' sense of humour was associated with mathematics grades.

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1.4 Null Hypotheses

The following six null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant association between students' perception of their teachers' general performance effectiveness and their performance in mathematics.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant association between students' perception of their teachers' clarity in communication effectiveness and their performance in mathematics.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant association between students' rating of their teachers' teaching skill effectiveness and their performance in mathematics.
- H₀₄:** There is no significant association between students' perception of their teachers' organising ability effectiveness and their performance in mathematics.
- H₀₅:** There is no significant association between students' perception of their teachers' cooperativeness effectiveness and their performance in mathematics.
- H₀₆:** There is no significant association between students' perception of their teachers' sense of humour effectiveness and their performance in mathematics.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on two theories – the classical conditioning theory and the cognitive/Gestalt theory. The classical conditioning theory, which was propounded by Pavlov in 1927, posits that learning occurs through the formation of associations between conditioned stimuli and conditioned responses. Shenker (2013) stated that students see human classical conditioning actively unfold in an entertaining, understandable and memorable demonstration. We can not only help students acquire good behaviours by establishing correct stimulus-response associations but also correct bad behaviours by changing the stimulus-responses they have already

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formed (Xiong, 2024). A skilled and encouraging teacher functions as a conditioned stimulus that brings out positive academic behaviour.

Also, the Cognitive/Gestalt Theory of Learning, first propounded by Max Wertheimer, Wolfgang Köhler, and Kurt Koffka (1912), holds that learners perceive their environment as organised, meaningful wholes rather than isolated sensory fragments (Pampas, 2025). The theory points out that students respond to the overall impression the teacher makes, rather than isolated teaching behaviours that may be occasional. Teachers can help students see how mathematical ideas connect to form a coherent whole, instead of presenting concepts as disconnected procedures.

2.2. Conceptual Framework

This study is focused on the idea that students' perceptions of their teachers are shaped by concrete, observable behaviours that teachers display in the course of delivering instruction. Amakyi and Adu-Aboagye (2016) conducted a study at the University of Cape Coast. The study revealed that students are capable of identifying and rating some specific teaching characteristics, which included preparation, knowledge, assessment, and interpersonal relationships, in consistent and meaningful ways. The findings showed that teacher preparation was the most highly rated dimension of effectiveness, confirming that students notice and respond to how ready a teacher appears to be.

Also, Latif and Miles (2013), who carried out a study at a Canadian university, ranked instructor knowledge, clarity of explanation, and preparedness as the three most important qualities of an effective teacher. The study showed that these perceptions varied by gender, cultural background, and year of study; this suggested that different student groups may prioritise different dimensions of teacher effectiveness. This information helps the present study to choose the dimensions and reinforce the relevance of exploring student perceptions in a specific Nigerian secondary school context.

At the secondary school level in Nigeria, Nakpodia (2011) found that students in Delta State correctly identified qualities such as subject matter knowledge, engaging discussion, clear communication, and fair personal contact as markers of an effective teacher. The study also revealed that male and female

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students do not significantly differ in their perception of effective teaching, a result that is useful context for the present study given its balanced male-female sample. Similarly, Gimba et al. (2018) examined science and technology teaching in Niger State; the study highlighted that poor teaching foundations, lack of real-life relevance in lessons, and insufficient planning all contribute to weak learning outcomes, especially in technical subjects like mathematics.

Based on the findings of these researchers, the conceptual framework for this study positions students' perceptions of teacher effectiveness as an independent variable measured across six dimensions: general performance, clarity in communication, teaching skill, organisational ability, cooperativeness, and sense of humour. These six dimensions are drawn from the Students' Perception of Teacher Effectiveness Scale (SPTES) and are expected to predict mathematics academic performance as the dependent variable. The framework assumes that positive perceptions across these dimensions will correspond with higher achievement scores, while negative or neutral perceptions will correlate with weaker performance outcomes.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The design was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to examine existing relationships between perception variables and academic outcomes without manipulation of variables. Survey designs are widely employed in educational psychology and have been validated for investigating attitudinal and perceptual constructs (Creswell, 2014).

3.2 Population and Sampling

The target population for this study comprised all the Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students enrolled in the fourteen (14) public secondary schools within Abak Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. According to the Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board records, there are 1,120 students at the time of this study.

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A two-stage sampling procedure was employed. In the first stage, five (5) schools were purposively selected from the fourteen to ensure representation across urban, semi-urban, and rural communities within the LGA. These five schools had a combined SS2 population of 520 students. In the second stage, a systematic random sampling technique was used to select students from each school; 20 students were selected from each school, giving a total sample of 100 students. Gender balance was maintained by ensuring that 50 male and 50 female students were included across the five schools. Of the 100 questionnaires administered, all 100 were returned and found usable, which represented a 100% response rate. This sample size was considered adequate for non-parametric correlation analysis at the 0.05 level of significance (Field, 2013).

3.3 Research Instrument

Data were collected using the Students' Perception of Teacher Effectiveness Scale (SPTES), a researcher-constructed structured questionnaire. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A gathered demographic information, while Section B contained 36 Likert-type items rated on a four-point scale (Strongly Agree = 4 to Strongly Disagree = 1) across six subscales: General Performance, Clarity in Communication, Teaching Skill, Organisational Ability, Cooperativeness, and Sense of Humour, corresponding to the study's hypotheses.

In addition, students' most recent mathematics examination grades were obtained from school records as the measure of academic performance. Face and content validity were established through expert review by three senior faculty members in the Department of Curriculum and Teaching at the University of Calabar. A pilot test administered to 20 students from a school outside the sampled schools yielded a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.81, confirming adequate internal consistency of the instrument.

3.4 Data Analysis

The data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Means and standard deviations were computed for all subscales and the criterion variable. Six null hypotheses were tested using the Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient (ρ) at the 0.05 level of significance.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the six subscales of teacher effectiveness and mathematics performance are summarised below. The overall mean rating for general teacher effectiveness was 3.21 (SD = 0.54), suggesting that students generally hold moderately positive perceptions of their mathematics teachers. Clarity in communication received the highest mean rating among all subscales (M = 3.34, SD = 0.49), while sense of humour received the lowest (M = 2.87, SD = 0.61). Mean mathematics examination scores across the sample averaged 52.4% (SD = 14.6), consistent with the pattern of moderate to low achievement documented in national examinations (WAEC, 2024).

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

4.2.1. Hypothesis One: General Performance Effectiveness and Mathematics Achievement.

A Spearman rank-order correlation was computed and yielded $\rho = 0.43$ ($p = 0.001$), indicating a moderate, statistically significant positive association. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. Students who viewed their teachers as generally effective tended to score higher in mathematics. This finding is consistent with Ayanwoye et al. (2024), who found that teacher personality and performance traits are meaningful predictors of student outcomes in Nigerian secondary schools.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two: Clarity in Communication and Mathematics Achievement.

The analysis yielded $\rho = 0.51$ ($p < 0.001$), the strongest correlation in the study. The null hypothesis was rejected. This result aligns with findings from multiple studies. Latif and Miles (2013) found that the ability to explain clearly was the most highly valued instructor quality among economics students in Canada. Amakyi and Adu-Aboagye (2016) similarly ranked clear explanation as the second most important effective teaching characteristic after preparation. Nakpodia (2011) highlighted explaining facts and ideas satisfactorily and engaging students in meaningful discussion as among the highest-rated teacher qualities by Nigerian

secondary school students. Together, these findings confirm that when students understand what is being taught, they perform better.

4.2.3. Hypothesis Three: Teaching Skill Effectiveness and Mathematics Achievement.

A significant positive correlation was found ($\rho = 0.46$, $p < 0.001$). The null hypothesis was rejected. Teaching skill, which includes the use of varied methods, relating lessons to real-life contexts, and pacing instruction appropriately, was meaningfully linked to student performance. This echoes the concern raised by Gimba et al. (2018), who noted that science and technology teachers in Nigeria often fail to link content to real-life situations, which contributes to poor student outcomes. Effective use of teaching skill reduces the abstract nature of subjects like mathematics and makes content more accessible.

4.2.4. Hypothesis Four: Organisational Ability and Mathematics Achievement.

The correlation was $\rho = 0.38$ ($p = 0.006$), which was statistically significant. The null hypothesis was rejected. Students who perceived their teachers as well-organised tended to achieve better in mathematics. Being organised, as Amakyi and Adu-Aboagye (2016) found, is closely tied to teacher preparation, the dimension rated most important in their study. When a teacher presents material in a clear, structured sequence and connects new content to prior knowledge, students are better positioned to understand and retain mathematical concepts.

4.2.5. Hypothesis Five: Teacher Cooperativeness and Mathematics Achievement.

The analysis yielded $\rho = 0.41$ ($p = 0.002$), a moderate and significant association. The null hypothesis was rejected. Students who felt their teachers were approachable, fair, and supportive performed better. This is consistent with Nakpodia's (2011) finding that establishing happy personal contact with students and attending to students' needs were among the most highly rated qualities of an effective teacher. It also aligns with the argument by Gimba et al. (2018) that when

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teachers create cooperative rather than competitive classroom environments, students develop more positive attitudes toward the subject.

4.2.6. Hypothesis Six: Sense of Humour and Mathematics Achievement.

This subscale produced the weakest correlation in the study ($\rho = 0.22$, $p = 0.031$), though it remained statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The null hypothesis was rejected, but the practical significance of this association is limited. Amakyi and Adu-Aboagye (2016) similarly found that sense of humour was among the lower-ranked effective teaching characteristics (ranked 35th out of 39), suggesting that while students value a pleasant classroom atmosphere, they do not see humour as a core driver of learning outcomes. This finding suggests that a sense of humour may serve more as a supportive factor than a direct predictor of performance.

4.3 Summary of Findings

All six null hypotheses were rejected. Statistically significant positive associations were found between each dimension of students' perception of teacher effectiveness and mathematics academic performance. The strongest predictor was perceived clarity in communication ($\rho = 0.51$), followed by teaching skill ($\rho = 0.46$), general effectiveness ($\rho = 0.43$), cooperativeness ($\rho = 0.41$), organisational ability ($\rho = 0.38$), and sense of humour ($\rho = 0.22$). These results reinforce the broader conclusion from the literature that students are reliable informants about teaching quality and that their perceptions carry real consequences for their academic outcomes.

5.1 Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between students' perception of teacher effectiveness and academic performance in mathematics among SS2 students in Abak Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The findings confirm that students' perceptions of their mathematics teachers across six dimensions are all positively and significantly associated with their mathematics achievement. Perceived clarity in communication emerged as the strongest predictor of performance, underlining the critical role of instructional communication in the teaching of a subject that many students find abstract and difficult.

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These findings are in line with a growing body of evidence from Nigeria and beyond that places the teacher at the centre of student learning outcomes (Nakpodia, 2011; Gimba et al., 2018; Amakyi & Adu-Aboagye, 2016; Latif & Miles, 2013). The consistent pattern across all six hypotheses reinforces the view that how students feel about their teacher is not merely attitudinal but carries measurable academic consequences. Students who perceive their teachers as clear, skilled, organised, cooperative, and generally effective tend to perform better in mathematics.

5.2 Recommendations

Mathematics teachers in Abak LGA and across Akwa Ibom State should prioritise clarity of explanation, structuring lessons in step-by-step ways that connect abstract mathematical ideas to familiar, real-world situations. School administrators and state educational authorities should include student perception data as a regular component of teacher appraisal processes, as students are well-positioned to provide actionable feedback on teaching quality. Professional development programmes for mathematics teachers should focus on communication skills, lesson organisation, and cooperative classroom management, as these dimensions showed the strongest links to student performance. Finally, future studies should expand the sample to include more LGAs and schools and should explore whether teacher perception mediates or moderates the effect of other factors, such as class size and instructional resources, on mathematics achievement.

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